

A Time Series Investigation of Currency Circulation Dynamics in Nigeria

C.A. Awogbemi ✉

Statistics Programme, National Mathematical Centre, Abuja, Nigeria

A.K. Ilori

Statistics Programme, National Mathematical Centre, Abuja, Nigeria

I. Muhammed

Department of Statistics, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, Nigeria

J. Daniel

Department of Mathematics & Statistics, Redeemer's University, Ede, Nigeria

H. Alilu

Department of Statistics, Nasarawa State University, Keffi, Nigeria

B.P. Huleji

Department of Statistics, Nasarawa State University, Keffi, Nigeria

M.S. Omotayo-Tomo

*Department of Mathematical Sciences,
Olusegun Agagu University of Science & Technology, Okitipupa, Nigeria*

B.I. Okafor

Department of Statistics, Federal University of Technology, Owerri, Nigeria

V.B. Paul

Department of Mathematics, Rivers State University, Port Harcourt, Nigeria

A.S. Johnson

Department of Statistics, Nasarawa State University, Keffi, Nigeria

A.O. Adejumo

Department of Statistics, University of Ilorin, Nigeria

Abstract

Currency in circulation (CIC) is the total value of physical currency (banknotes and coins) held by the public, businesses, and financial institutions outside the central bank's vaults. In this study, a time series analysis is conducted to uncover the dynamics of currency in circulation, focusing on its underlying patterns, trends and relationships, using a monthly dataset spanning from 2009 to 2024. SARIMA techniques were used to model the data and it was observed that seasonal ARIMA (0,1,1) (0,0,1) [12] best fit the data with an AIC and BIC of 4945.67 and 4955.31 respectively. This indicates the presence of both seasonal and non-seasonal fluctuations in currency circulation as a result of GDP, inflation, interest rates and the impacts of digital solutions and financial inclusion initiatives. The forecast result showed that the currency in circulation shall be stationary in line with the present state for the next twenty months.

Keywords: *Time series, Currency, SARIMA, Stationary Test, Differencing.*

Suggested citation: Awogbemi, C.A., Ilori, A. K., Muhammed, I., Daniel, J., Alilu, H., Huleji, B.P., Omotayo-Tomo, M.S., Okafor, B.I., Paul, V.B., Johnson, A.S., & Adejumo, A.O. (2025). A Time Series Investigation of Currency Circulation Dynamics in Nigeria. *Scientia. Technology, Science and Society*, 2(6), 54-61. DOI: 10.59324/stss.2025.2(6).06

Introduction

The concept of currency in circulation (CIC) is simply the quantity of cash in hand used throughout the country's economy to purchase goods and services. According to Stavreski (1998), the relevance of currency in circulation in every economy is driven by two significant indicators vis-à-vis: the ratio of currency in circulation to the gross domestic product and the ratio of currency-to-money supply. As one of the most influential components of liquid asset classes, CIC can pose a challenge to an economy. Hence, the need for the monetary authority to give thorough attention to controlling the situation of currency in circulation given the fact that an upswing in currency demand can constrain or boost liquidity (Albert et al, 2013; Evans, 1998; Evans and Richard, 1999). In the short run, the demand for liquidity is influenced by seasonal factors and unusual incidents like retrospective hikes in wages, which can be identified through historical trends (Yin-wong and Menzie, 2001). Several studies have been conducted on the placement of currency in circulation in an economy (Dornbusch, 1976; Vermeulen et al, 2016).

Luguterah et al (2013) presented a predictive model for monthly currency in circulation in Ghana and concluded that ARIMA (0,1,1)(0,1,1)₁₂ model was appropriate for modelling the Currency in Circulation.

Alvan (2014) studied modeling and forecasting currency in circulation for liquidity management in Nigeria, with the result that the most accurate models were mixed models with structural as well as ARIMA components augmented by seasonal and dummy variables. He concluded that the exchange rate, interbank rate, seasonality, holidays and elections were significant in explaining the demand for currency.

Abubakar et al (2018) adopted the ARIMA model to study the status of currency in circulation in Nigeria and revealed that among the 12 postulated ARIMA models, ARIMA(1,1,0) produced the best model as it gives the least value of AIC and BIC.

Bamanga and Adams (2022) presented predictive modelling of Nigeria's currency in circulation using the United State Census Bureau's X-12 ARIMA Seasonal adjustment software. The study concluded on the basis of the data used, that X-12-ARIMA (2 1 1)(0 1 1) is the most accurate forecasting approach for Nigeria's CIC.

Torutein and Emmanuel (2022) carried out a study on the influence of currency in circulation on the economic performance in Nigeria affirming that contrary to expectations, the coefficient of the currency in circulation when lagged by one period is positive but statistically insignificant at 5%. The researchers concluded that the monetary policies adopted by the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) are way ineffective in promoting economic growth.

In the follow-up to previous studies and in the face of the current realities of the Nigerian economy alongside time lag, this research is interested in exploring currency circulation dynamics: trends, patterns, and forecasting into and beyond 2024 using time series perspectives.

Methodology

This study uses monthly data on the currency in circulation in Nigeria from January 2009 to May 2024 and was obtained from the database of the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN).

Seasonal ARIMA Model

The seasonal Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (SARIMA) model was used to model the data for the currency in circulation. If a seasonal component exists in a dataset, then ARIMA (p, d, q) is extended to include the seasonal component. An ARIMA (p, d, q) model contains an Autoregressive (AR) part indicating a relationship between present and past values, a random value and a Moving Average (MA) part which implies the present value has a relationship with the past shocks. In that sense, the SARIMA model is expressed as ARIMA (p, d, q) (P, D, Q)_S. The orders p and q respectively represent the non-seasonal AR and MA components. The orders P and Q as well represent the seasonal AR and MA components. Seasonal and non-seasonal differencing are D and d respectively. The SARIMA model denoted by ARIMA (p, d, q) (P, D, Q)_S can be expressed using the backshift operator as;

$$\phi(B)\Phi(B^s)(1-B)^d(1-B)^D = \theta(B)\Theta(B^s)\varepsilon_t, \quad (1)$$

where

$$\phi(B) = 1 - \phi_1 B - \phi_2 B^2 - \dots - \phi_p B^p \quad (2)$$

$$\Phi(B^s) = 1 - \Phi_1 B^s - \Phi_2 B^{2s} - \dots - \Phi_p B^{ps} \quad (3)$$

$$\theta(B) = 1 - \theta_1 B - \theta_2 B^2 - \dots - \theta_q B^q \quad (4)$$

$$\Theta(B^s) = 1 - \Theta_1 B^s - \Theta_2 B^{2s} - \dots - \Theta_p B^{ps} \quad (5)$$

B represents the backshift operator;

ε_t represents white noise error term at period t ;

ϕ represents the parameters of the non-seasonal autoregressive component;

Φ represents the parameters of the seasonal autoregressive component;

θ represents the parameters of the non-seasonal moving average component;

Θ represents the parameters of the moving average component;

Stationarity Test

This test of stationarity was performed on the data of Currency in Circulation using the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test which is based on the assumption that a time series data Y_t follows a random walk:

$$Y_t = \rho Y_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t \quad (6)$$

where $\rho = 1$, thus, Y_{t-1} is subtracted from both sides. $\Delta Y_t = \beta Y_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t$ and $\beta = \rho - 1$. The null hypothesis is $H_0 : \beta = 0$ and therefore $\rho = 1$ against the alternative that $H_1 : \beta < 0$ and $\rho < 1$. If the p -value of the associated coefficient β is less than the 0.05 significance level, then the data is stationary (Luguterah et al., 2013).

Model Selection Process

Akaike Information Criteria (AIC) and the Swartz Information Criteria (SIC) are computed using the log-likelihood estimates. They are computed as follows;

$$AIC = -2 \left(\frac{l}{n} \right) + \frac{2k}{n}, \quad (7)$$

where

l = the maximum likelihood function

n = number of observations and

k = number of parameters

$$SIC = -2 \left(\frac{ll}{n} \right) + \frac{k(\ln(n))}{n} \quad (8)$$

From the foregoing, the model having the minimum AIC or SIC represents the true model and, may be interpreted as the best approximating model among the candidates of models being considered.

Forecast Model Adequacy Check

Following the forecast, a check of the model adequacy was made using the Box- Ljung test to check for higher-order autocorrelation and homoscedasticity accordingly. The test statistic for the Box-Ljung test is as follows:

$$Q = \frac{n(n+2)}{(n-k)} \sum_1^h P_k^2, \tag{9}$$

where

n for the sample size

h number of lag being tested

P_k sample autocorrelation at lag k

The test statistic Q follows a chi-square distribution with h degrees of freedom; i.e.,

$Q: \chi^2(h)$ such that we reject the null hypothesis H_0 when $Q > \chi_{1-\alpha, h}^2$ and conclude that autocorrelation is present in the model.

Discussion of Results

The analysis of the currency in circulation dataset is presented in Figures and Tables.

Figure 1. Time Plot of Currency in Circulation

Figure 2. Plot of ACF for Currency in Circulation

Figure 3. Plot of PACF for Currency in Circulation

Table 1. Summary Statistics of the Currency in Circulation

Minimum	1 st Quartile	Median	Mean	3 rd Quartile	Maximum
982098	1438617	1781046	1953449	2329707	3965101

Table 2. Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test

Dickey-Fuller	Lag order	p-value
-3.1426	5	0.09937

Table 3. SARIMA(0,1,1)(0,0,1)[12]

Model	ma1	sma1
Coefficients	-0.3352	0.2405
S.E.	0.0683	0.0709

$$y_t = -0.3352\varepsilon_{t-1} + 0.2405\varepsilon_{t-12}$$

AIC=4945.67; BIC = 4955.31; Log likelihood = -2469.83

Table 4: Forecast Value for the Currency in Circulation from the Best-Fitted Model

Months	Point Forecast	LCI 80%	HCI 80%	LCI 95%	HCI 95%
Jun 2024	4001090	3790989	4211191	3679768	4322412
Jul 2024	4000703	3650222	4351184	3464689	4536718
Aug 2024	4017651	3568729	4466574	3331084	4704219
Sept 2024	4041543	3512180	4570906	3231952	4851134
Oct 2024	4098985	3499886	4698084	3182742	5015228
Nov 2024	4190013	3528489	4851537	3178299	5201727
Dec 2024	4274103	3555557	4992649	3175182	5373025
Jan 2025	4367094	3595730	5138459	3187394	5546794
Feb 2025	4400420	3579629	5221211	3145129	5655711
Mar 2025	4402065	3534660	5269470	3075483	5728647
April 2025	4376226	3464587	5287866	2981995	5770458
May 2025	4377615	3423791	5331439	2918867	5836363
June 2025	4380934	3371290	5390579	2836817	5925052
July 2025	4380934	3313000	5448869	2747669	6014200
Aug 2025	4380934	3257730	5504139	2663141	6098728

Sept 2025	4380934	3205055	5556814	2582582	6179287
Oct 2025	4380934	3154641	5607228	2505481	6256388
Nov 2025	4380934	3106219	5655650	2431426	6330443
Dec 2025	4380934	3059571	5702298	2360083	6401786
Jan 2026	4380934	3014514	5747355	2291174	6470695

Figure 4. Forecast Plot Using the Best Seasonal ARIMA Model for Currency in Circulation

Box-Ljung Test

$$\chi^2 = 11.072, df = 12, p\text{-value} = 0.5227$$

Table 1 shows that the minimum currency in circulation from the period covered is 982098 while the maximum is 3,965,101 with an average value of 1,953,449. The gradual decaying positive spikes in Figure 2 indicate non-stationarity in the data and alongside Figure 3. The spikes growing beyond the confidence bounds imply that additional information still exists in residuals to be tapped. The ADF test in Table 1 below validates the non-stationarity status of the currency in the circulation dataset with a p-value of 0.0322.

The Seasonal ARIMA(0,1,1)(0,0,1)[12] model presented in Table 2 shows that a non-seasonal pattern exists in the data exhibiting insignificant autoregressive effect (AR(1)=0), of no autocorrelation. The difference parameter d=1 indicates non-stationarity and the moving average term MA(1)= -0.3352 captures short-time fluctuations. Seasonal pattern also exists as shown from the seasonal moving average term SMA(1)= 0.2405 indicating a moderate seasonal effect with a period of 12 months.

Table 4 and Figure 4 display the forecast from the best SARIMA model for twenty (20) upfront and it was observed that at a 95% confidence interval, the currency in circulation will remain stationary as it currently stands. Consequently, the Box-Ljung test with a test value of 11.072 and p-value of 0.5227 validates the forecast reliability.

Conclusion

This study explores currency circulation dynamics: trends, patterns, and forecasting into and beyond 2024 using time series perspectives. The result shows that the currency in circulation dataset was non-stationary at first instance and after first differencing, the seasonal ARIMA (0,1,1)(0,0,1)[12] model provides the suited model for forecasting. From the result of the forecast,

it can be concluded that the status of currency in circulation shall remain within the current state for the next twenty months. The study, therefore, recommends that the seasonal ARIMA (0,1,1)(0,0,1)[12] model should be employed to fit the future currency circulation situation in Nigeria.

Acknowledgements

The authors wish to express their gratitude to the Management of the National Mathematical Centre (NMC), Abuja, Nigeria for the opportunity given to the authors to participate in the Research Oriented Course (ROC) in Time Series Analysis & Applications.

References

- Abubakar, B., Bako, N., Shelleng, A. U., & Kawu, A. J. (2018). Time series modelling of currency in circulation in Nigeria using ARIMA model. *BIMA Journal of Science and Technology*, 2(2), 216–226.
- Albert, L., Suleman, N., & Lea, A. (2013). A predictive model for monthly currency circulation in Ghana. *Mathematical Theory and Modeling*, 3(4), 43–52.
- Alvan, A. (2014). Modelling and forecasting currency in circulation for liquidity management in Nigeria. *CBN Journal of Applied Statistics*, 5(1), 78–104.
- Bamanga, M. A., & Adams, S. O. (2022). Predictive modeling of Nigeria's currency in circulation using X-12 autoregressive integrated moving average method. *Dutch Journal of Finance and Management*, 5(1), Article 21473, 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.55267/djfm/13340>
- Dornbusch, R. (1976). Expectations and exchange rate dynamics. *Journal of Political Economy*, 84, 1161–1176.
- Evans, M. D. D. (1998). *The microstructure of foreign exchange dynamics* [Unpublished manuscript]. Georgetown University.
- Evans, M. D. D., & Richard, K. L. (1999). Order flow and exchange rate dynamics (NBER Working Paper No. 7317, pp. 1–43). National Bureau of Economic Research.
- Luguterah, A., Nasiru, S., & Anzagra, L. (2013). A predictive model for monthly currency in Ghana. *Mathematical Theory and Modeling*, 3(4), 44–52.
- Stavreski, Z. (1998). Currency in circulation: National Bank of the Republic of Macedonia (Working Paper No. 1, pp. 1–14).
- Torutein, I. O., & Emmanuel, B. (2022). Influence of currency in circulation on economic performance in Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Management Sciences*, 23(1), 229–243.
- Vermeulen, C., Bosch, A., Joubert, F., & Rossouw, J. (2016). Can currency in circulation predict South African economic activity? *Economic Research Southern Africa Working Paper No. 532*, 1–23.
- Yin-Wong, C., & Menzie, D. C. (2001). Currency traders and exchange rate dynamics: A survey of the US market. *CEifo Working Paper Series No. 251*, 1–42.

